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Maker education activities and their effect on creativity and self-efficacy

The EU project DOIT has developed and tested an early entrepreneurial education programme in makerspace settings for children between the age of six and sixteen, involving 989 children in a series of two pilot phases in 10 European countries. The number of makerspaces and FabLabs, i.e. open workshops that grant access to digital technologies and tools such as 3D printers and laser cutters, globally raised rapidly since its first foundation in 2002 at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Maker spaces and “maker pedagogy” found their entrance also in (formal) education (Craddock, 2015; Dougherty, 2016). Meanwhile, ever more schools have their own maker spaces, while others do collaborate with maker spaces in their region.

The DOIT programme

The pedagogy of making builds on several pedagogical pioneers, from reform pedagogues to constructivists, from Montessori (2013) to Piaget and Papert (Ackermann, 2001), who all support self-regulated learning (van Hout-Wolters et al., 2000), where learners decide on their learning goals as well as on time and method. In this open learning setting teachers acquire the role of tutors assisting the learner in their learning paths. Making is hands-on learning, where makers learn from others in a process of trial and error, often in interdisciplinary and collaborative teams (Bell, 2010; Bruffee, 1993; Kaltman, 2010). Acknowledging that all these principles matched the conditions for entrepreneurial education, the DOIT project has incorporated the maker pedagogical approach.

The developed DOIT programme consists of seven consecutive elements with a minimum course length of 15 hours. It starts with a Motivation phase where students envision the scope of their possibilities for tackling challenges of their personal environments. The second phase is about Co-design: Students are asked to collect and select potential ideas for innovations. In the Co-creation phase students gather in teams and develop first prototypes. In the Iteration phase, the prototype is continuously improved and in the next step, in the Reflection phase, feedback on the prototypes is exchanged between the teams. In the last two steps, Scaling and Reaching Out, the robustness of the prototype is tested with a bigger group of users and finally students share their projects with a wider public.

Students, for instance, came up with ideas for a prototype that would send an alarm in case of risk of flooding of the little creek on the mountain pasture, or they would develop a monster that eats garbage. The focus lies not on a fully functionally final prototype, but the programme rather aimed at encouraging the development of

own ideas, believing in them and to work together on a prototype that would illustrate their idea in a tangible way.

The DOIT programme is inspired by the definition provided by Eurydice on entrepreneurship education, which acknowledges “... learners developing the skills and mind-set to be able to turn creative ideas into entrepreneurial action. This is a key competence for all learners, supporting personal development, active citizenship, social inclusion and employability” (Eurydice, 2016). Further, following Lackéus (2015) who distinguishes between entrepreneurial knowledge, skills and attitude, DOIT clearly focuses on the latter two.

In line with these core principles the evaluative dimensions were defined for measuring the effect on a personal level: *creativity, self-efficacy, teamwork and collaboration skills, dealing with uncertainty, perseverance, empathy and knowing others' needs, motivation and sense of initiative and planning and management skills*. While the first two ones are assessed quantitatively and qualitatively, the other seven dimensions were assessed qualitatively. In this paper we focus on the effect on the two dimensions, creativity and self-efficacy, which are to be found at the core of similar evaluation frameworks, e.g. Entrecomp (Bacigalupo et al., 2016).

Evaluation methods and results

For measuring creativity, the Test for Creative Thinking - Drawing Production (TCT-DP; in German: TDS-Z, Urban & Jellen, 2010) was chosen as being suitable for DOIT as it is a language free test, which can easily be used in different countries and also for the age range. It further provides for so called parallel versions: a Form A for the pre-test, and a form B for the post-test.

As for measuring self-efficacy there was no published questionnaire available that was suitable for the quite large age range, we constructed a survey that is based on published scales with adaptations on item level (Boyd & Vozikis, 1994; Deusinger, 1986; Krampen, 1991; Midgley et al., 2000). The survey was translated into the different national languages. In filling in the questionnaire, younger children were assisted by facilitators, while children from eight years would autonomously fill in the survey.

Our statistical analysis shows significant effects of the DOIT action in both, in terms of creativity and self-efficacy with moderate effect sizes of 0.243 and 0.207.

Interestingly, in contrast to the assumption that creativity would correlate with age, the younger age group (6-10 years) showed the same level of creativity as the older age group (11-16 years) in the pre-test. In the post-test both age groups gained significantly higher creativity scores, although the older age group obviously benefitted more from the DOIT action in terms of creativity.

Both age groups have about the same level of self-efficacy in the beginning of the DOIT action but younger ones tend to have higher scores afterwards. Thus, in contrast to creativity, where the older ones gained higher scores in the post-test, it is the younger ones who outscore the older ones in the self-efficacy survey.

In order to prove that the score gain in the creativity test and the self-efficacy survey can be attributed to the DOIT action and not to other confounding variables (Bortz & Döring, 2013), we have created a “quasi” control group within our dataset with children who did not fulfil the minimum requirement of attending at least 15 hours of the programme. When we compare the creativity test of these two groups (experiential group with at

least 15 hours attended and control group with fewer hours) then we see that the experimental group increased their score significantly while the control group did not. The same applies to the self-efficacy survey.

Conclusions

The call for maker pedagogy in formal and informal education is often argued with equipping children with 21st skills (Ananiadou & Claro, 2009). Moreover, that making can also constitute means for fostering entrepreneurial thinking and developing core entrepreneurial skills and attitudes has been neglected so far and firstly been introduced in the DOIT project as an innovative approach. The results show significant benefits for the participants in terms of creativity and self-efficacy which are prerequisites for developing own ideas and believing in them.

The evaluation design follows a pre-post comparison of the scores, comparing the scores before and after taking part in DOIT. Thus, the analysis cannot anticipate any long-term changes. However, we can conclude that making approaches with young children can contribute to some extent to the development of entrepreneurial skills and attitudes.

Although these open learning settings challenge students as well as facilitators, these types of learning settings adapt well to the next generations' challenges of creativity and problem-solving attributes for social innovation development. Although a follow-up study after several months would be insightful it could not be undertaken in the framework of the project. Moreover, a better understanding of the relationship between age and the resulting benefits in creativity. Such insights could then inform pedagogical strategies in open learning settings.

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